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Checklists of the coccoid species known to exist in Egypt Part I: Family Diaspididae (Hemiptera: Coccoidea) (1902 - 2025)

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Abstract

The armored scale insects (Diaspididae) represented one of the largest families of super family Coccoidea in Egypt. The present checklist of 52 genera and 107 species of Diaspididae including common names, Arabic names, Literature records and reported made by the Senior authors in Egypt. There are seven species are added to the diaspididae fauna namely: *Chionaspis cryphaeformis* Newsfeed, *Chionaspis gryphaeformis* Newsfeed, *Comstockaspis perniciosus* (Comstock) = *Quadraspidiotus perniciosus* Ferris. , *Diaspidiotus ostreaformis* (Curtis) = *Quadraspidiotus ostreaformis* (Curtis), *Duplachionapis monodi* (Rungs) = *Chionaspis noueae monodi* Rungs, *Howardia biclavis* (Comstock) and *Parlatoria chinensis* (Marlatt).

Introduction

Family Diaspididae is one of neococcoid species which known as armored scale insects or true scale insects. The first comprehensive and checklist of Diaspididae of Egypt was published by Hall (1922-1927) containing 60 species, Ezzat (1958) 68 species in his taxonomic Key, Ezzat and Nada (1987), Abd-Rabou, 2000, 2001 and 2012, Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996, published subsequent checklists of the Diaspididae known to exist in Egypt. Recently, several authors have reported on the scale insects known on exist in Egypt, included diaspidid species (Moursi and Gomaa, 1991, Moursi *et al.*, 1996, Abou-Elkhair, 2001, Mohammad and Ghabbour, 2008 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021). Here, the update the annotated checklist of Diaspididae in Egypt, based on

literature data. Diaspididae has two subfamilies, Aspidiotinae and Diaspididae. Subfamily Aspidiotinae has 4 tribes. Aspidiotini, Leucospidini, Parlatorini, Odonaspidini (According to Balachowsky, 1948). Subfamily Diaspidinae has two tribes Diaspidini and Lepidasaphidini (According to Takagi, 1970). The list of species (107 species) recorded from 1907 to 2024 in Egypt. Ordered here as alphabetical.

1. *Acanthomytilus intermittans* (Hall) *Lepidosaphes intermittans* Hall

Common name: Desert grass scale and African fodder cane scale

حشرة النجيل القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1924 as *Imperata cylindrica* in Nagaa Hamady and on *Pinnisetum dichotomum* in Wady Degla.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958, Ezzat and Afifi, 1966 on *Saccharum spontaneum*,

Ezzat and Nada, 1987, Moursi and Gomaa, 1991 on *Panicum* sp. at Omayed site. In Northwestern Coast. Ghbbour and Mohmmad, 1996 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 9 genera of family Poaceae in 13 countries.

2. *Acanthomytilus sacchari* (Hall)

***Lepidosaphes sacchari* Hall**

Common name: Saccharum Scale

حشرة السكر القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 and 1924 as *Lepidosaphes sacchari* on *Saccharum officinarum*. in Giza and Embaba.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958 as *Lepidosaphes sacchari*, Ezzat and Afifi, 1966 on *Arundo donax*, *Imperata cylindrical*, *Phragmites australis*, *Saccharum spontaneam*. Ezzat and Nada, 1987, Ghbbour and Mohammad, 1996 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 10 genera of 2 families in 12 countries.

3. *Adiscodaspis ericicola* (Malenotti)

***Adiscodaspis tamaricicola* Malenotti**

***Prodiaspis tamaricicola* (Malenotti)**

Common name: Tamarix Scale and White tamarix Scale.

حشرة العبل القشرية

Recorded by: Malenotti, 1916 in Egypt on Tamarix.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 on Tamarix at Matariya, Ezzat, 1958 as *Rugaspidotus tamaricicola* (Mall.), Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *Adiscodaspis tamaricicola*, Abd-Rabou, 2000 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021 as *A. ericicola* in New Valley Governorate.

Note: Hall, 1922 mentioned that this species of a very interesting genus as the usual pygidial characters of the Diapridinae are entirely absent.

Lindinger, 1936 and Balachowsky, 1953 showed that *A. ericicola* and *A. tamaricicola* were considered to be synonyms. There are no sequanes hairs or bulbous and circum genital glands are also wanting.

Associated with 2 genera of 2 families in 19 countries.

4. *Aonidia lauri* (Bouché)

***Aspidiotus lauri* Bouché**

Common name: Bay scale and Laural scale.

حشرة الغار القشرية

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958 for the first time on *Laurus nobilis*; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with all genera of family Lauraceae in 35 countries.

5. *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell)

***Chrysomphalus aurantii* Hall**

***Aspidiotus aurantii* Maskell**

Common name: California red scale and red Scale

الحشرة القشرية الحمراء

Recorded by: Hall, 1922, as a main pest of citrus all over Egypt. He recorded it as *Chrysomphalus aurantij*.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 on *Morus*, *Phoenix dactylifera*, *Olea*, *Phyllanthus*, *Pinus*, *Malus domestica* and *Prunus domestica*; Balachowsky, 1932; Ezzat, 1958 and Ezzat and Nada, 1987 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021 on *Ficus virens* and *Musa acuminatum*.

Associated with 207 genera of 91 families in 134 countries.

6. *Aonidiella citrina* (Coquillett)

***Aspidiotus citrinus* Coquillett**

Common name: Yellow scale.

الحشرة القشرية الصفراء

Recorded by: Abd-Rabou, 2000, who mentioned that it's not recorded in Egypt before and

Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 66 genera of 40 families in 61 countries.

7. *Aonidiella orientalis* (Newstead)

***Aspidiotus orientalis* Newstead**

Common name: Oriental scale

Recorded by: Elwan, 2000 on *Phoenix dactylifera* in Al-Dakhliya, not recorded in Egypt before; **Abou-Elkhair**, 2001 and EFSA, 2022.

Reported by: Williams and Watson, 1988 reported that it is polyphagous.

Note: It differs from *A. aurantii* and *A. citrina* in having perivulvar pores, groups of dorsal submarginal macroducts on prepygidial segments (Watson and Kendo, 2022).

It has been recorded from hosts in 189 genera of 77 plant families in 72 countries and it can attack any host except conifers.

8. *Aspidaspis longiloba* (Hall)

Aspidaspis longilobus (Hall).

Targionia longiloba (Hall)

Common name: Longtailed scale.

الحشرة القشرية ذات الأهداب الطويلة

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 on Tamarix at Armant, Upper Egypt as *Targionia longiloba*. It is found in Egypt only.

Reported by: Balachowsky, 1950 and 1958; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *Aspidaspis longilobus*; Mohammad and Ghabbour, 2008 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Infests 2 genera *Atraphaxis spinosa* (Polygonaceae) & *Tamarix* spp. (Tamaricaceae).

9. *Aspidiotus destructor* Signoret

Temnaspidotus destructor Signoret

Common name: Coconut scale, coconut false scale and bourbon scale

حشرة جوز الهند القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 who mentioned that it was collected in 1917 in one of the biggest nursery gardens in Cairo on a plant not stated.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Danzig and Pellizzari, 1998 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 142 genera of 73 families in 119 countries

10. *Aspidiotus nerii* (Bouché)

Aspidiotus hederæ (Vallot)

Common name: Ivy scale and oleander scale.

حشرة التفلة القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 and 1923 as *Aspidiotus hederæ* on *Urena lobata* at Giza Garden of Horticultural section of the Ministry of Agriculture. He mentioned that it is very frequently

found on lemons imported from Cyprus and other Mediterranean countries.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Abd-Rabou, 2000; Mesbah *et al.*, 2001a on *Acacia stenophylla*, *A. saligna* at Burg el-Arab and Abbas; Badr, 2014 on pine trees and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 325 genera of 120 families in 73 countries.

11. *Aulacaspis crawii* (Cockerell)

Diaspis crawii Cockerell

Common name: Azedruch scale.

حشره الزنزلخت القشريه

Reported by: Giliomee, 1966 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: It is close to *Aulacaspis spinosa* but differ by the 2nd stage female with only 4 marginal macroducts on each side of the pygidium and the presence of double rows of submedial macroducts on the 1st abdominal segment (Tang, 1986).

Associated with 20 genera of 16 families in 9 countries.

12. *Aulacaspis rosae* (Bouché)

Aspidiotus rosae Bouché

Common name: Rose scale and rose hard scale.

حشرة الورد القشرية

Recorded by: Archangelskaya, 1937.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Giliomee, 1966; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Watson, 2002 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 20 genera of 11 families in 79 countries.

13. *Aulacaspis tubercularis*

(Newstead)

Aulacaspis (Diaspis) tubercularis Newstead

Aulacaspis cinnamomi mangifera (Newstead)

Common name: Cinnamon scale and white mango scale.

حشرة المانجو القشرية البيضاء

Recorded by: Newstead, 1911 from material collected at Helwan and sent by Willcocks, 1910 who mentioned

that it brought to Egypt with mango trees from Cylon.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 as *Diaspis cinnamoni* in Helwan mango trees; Ezzat, 1958 as *Aulacaspis cinnamomi* var *Mangifera*; Watson, 2002; Miller and Davidson, 2005 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 39 genera of 23 families in 81 countries.

14. *Avidovaspis phoenicis* Gerson and Davidson.

Common name: Pinnae date palm scale.

Recorded by: This species doesn't find in any country except Egypt (Gerson and Davidson, 1974), who collected it in 1968 on Pinnae of date palm, *Phoenix dactylifera* at Wadi Ferran, Sinai Peninsula.

Reported by: Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with one genus (*Phoenix* species) of one family in Egypt only.

15. *Carulaspis Juniperi* (Bouché) *Aspidiutus juniperi* Bouché

Common name: Juniper scale.

Reported by: Miller and Davidson, 2005 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: It is often misidentified as *C. visci* and *C. minima* but differ in the pygidium with a marginal macroduct and gland spines between the medium lobes and abdominal segment vi without submarginal macroducts dorsally (Deitz, 1979).

Associated with 18 genera of 4 families in 43 countries.

16. *Carulaspis minima* (Signoret)

***Diaspis minima* Signoret**

***Diaspis carueli* Targioni Tozzetti**

Common name: Juniper scale, cedar Scale and minute Cypress scale.

حشرة برمودا القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 as *Diaspis carueli* on *Thuja* sp. and *Cupressus* sp. in Upper and Lower Egypt. *C. minima* has been used as senior name by several authors.

Reported by: Moursi *et al.*, 1991b on *Thuja orientalis*; Moursi *et al.*, 1996 on fig trees at Burg el Arab site; **Abou-Elkhair**, 2001 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 16 genera of 4 families in 49 countries.

17. *Carulaspis visci* (Schrank)

***Coccus visci* Schrank**

Common name: Mistletoe scale

حشرة الهدال القشرية

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958 for the first time; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Abd-Rabou, 2000 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: It is confusing with *C. minima* and *C. carueli* but it causes galls in the formed rounded swelling of the host leaves, and the scale is deeply imbedded in the center of cavity lined and covered with follicle (**Goidanich**, 1960).

Associated with *Junipers* sp. and *Thuja* sp. of family Cupressaceas and *Viscum album* of family Santalaceae in 21 countries.

18. *Chionaspis cryphaeformis*

Newstead

Common name: Unknown.

Recorded by: Not recorded in any country except Egypt (Newstead, 1907).

Associated with 1 genus of 1 family in Egypt only.

19. *Chionaspis etrusca* Leonardi

Common name: Tamarix scale and tamarix scurly scale.

Reported by: Balachowsky, 1958 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with *Guercus* sp. (Fagaceae), *Tilia* sp. (Malvaceae), *Myricaria* sp. and *Tamarix* sp. (Tamaricaceae) 4 genera of 3 Families in 32 countries.

20. *Chionaspis gryphaeformis*

Newstead

Common name: Unknown.

Recorded by: Not recorded in any country except Egypt (Newstead, 1906).

Associated with 1 genus of 1 family in Egypt only.

21. *Chortinaspis senapirensis* Ben-Dov

Common name: Unknown

Recorded by: Not found in any country except Egypt. **Ben-Dov**, 1976 on *Panicum turgidum* in Sinai Peninsula, Senapir Island.

Reported by: Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with one genus (*Panicum turgidum*) of Family Poaceae in Egypt only.

22. *Chrysomphalus aonidium* (Linnaeus)

***Coccus aonidium* Linnaeus**

***Chrysomphalus ficus* Ashmed**

Common name: Black scale and circular black scale.

الحشرة القشرية السوداء

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 and 1923 as *Aspidiotus Ficus* = *Chrysomphalus aonidium*.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Habib *et al.*, 1960 on *Ficus retusa* and *Ficus religiosa*; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 199 genera of 80 families in 127 countries.

23. *Chrysomphalus dictyospermi* (Morgan)

***Aspidiotus dictyospermi* Morgan**

Common name: Dictyospermum scale and morgan's scale.

حشرة الديكتوسبيرما القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1925

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Mourad *et al.*, 2001 on *Hibiscus mutabilis* and *Nerium oleander* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: It is widely distributed in subtropical regions, very polyphagous, recorded as a most serious *Citrus* pest (CABI, 1951).

Associated with 211 genera of 84 families in 144 countries.

24. *Clavaspidotus apicalis* Takagi

Common name: False coconut scale.

Recorded by: Takagi, 1974 on *Pangium*, *Litsea* and citrus.

Reported by: Mohammad and Ghabbour, 2008 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 3 genera of 3 families [*Pangium* (Achariaceae), *Litsea glutinose* (Lauraceae) and citrus (Rutaceae)] in 4 counties.

25. *Comstockaspis perniciosus* (Comstock)

***Diaspidiotus perniciosus* (Comstock)**

***Aspidiotus perniciosus* Comstock**

***Quadraspidotus perniciosus* Ferris**

Common name: Som Jose scale, chines scale and California scale.

البرتشيزا القشرية وسان جوزيه القشرية

Recorded by: It is not recorded in Egypt before according to the cited lists of Coccoidea by Hall (1922, 1923 and 1924), or Ezzat, 1958, Ezzat and Nada, 1987. Also, the assigned distribution. maps in 1951 (CWIE), 2006, (EPPO, 2022) and 2006. (Zip Cood 200) didn't showed the presence or any record of the insect in Egypt.

Reported by: In 2001, it had been observed by Moursi; as *Quadraspidotus* for the first time in Egypt in few numbers on apple trees at Beheira Governorate (Kafr EL-Dawar). After that it observed in large number at Burg el-Arab area in 2002 and 2003 infesting apple trees, then it translocated on pear trees at the area in 2004 (Moursi *et al.*, 2008). The Specimens collected were identified by Watson

Associated with 80 genera of 43 families in 84 countries.

26. *Contigaspis bilobis* (Newstead)

***Chionaspis bilobis* Newstead**

Common name: Bilobe scale.

الحشرة القشرية ذات الهدبين

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 as *Chionaspis bilobis* on *Pithyranthus tortuosus* at Helwan.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958 as *Pinnaspis bilobis* on *Ochradenus buccatus*, Ezzat and Nada, 1987,

Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Panicum targidum*, *Fersetia*, *Capparis spinosa* and

Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 9 genera of 7 families in 4 countries.

27. *Contigaspis farsetiae* (Hall)

***Coccomytilus farsetiae* Hall**

***Artemaspis fursetiae* (Hall)**

Common name: Fersetia scale.

حشرة الفيرسينيا القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1926 as

Artemaspis farsetiae on *Fersetia aegyptiaca* at Masara, Cairo for the first time.

Reported by: Bodenheimer, 1929 on *Halaxylon* sp. as *Targionia duplides* at Sinai Peninsula; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *Artimaspsis panisebice* on *Fersetia aegyptia* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 15 genera of 10 families in 9 countries.

28. *Contigaspis zillae* (Hall)

***Eremaspis zillae* (Hall)**

***Pinnaspis zillae* Hall**

Common name: Zilla Scale

حشرة الزلة القشرية

حشرة السلة القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 on *Zilla spinosa* in Mokattam Hill, desert east of Cairo.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958 as *Pinnaspis zillae*; **Borchsenius** and Williams, 1963 as *Cantigaspsis zillae*

Ezzat and Afifi, 1966 on *Telephium pharospermum*, *Farsetia aegyptiacus*, *Zilla spinosu* at Wadi Hoff and on *Ochrodenus baccatus* in El-Maasara and Wadi Hoff; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Moursi and Gomma, 1991 on *Limoniastrum monopetalum* leaves and branches under dry system at Omayed site, Egyptian western desert and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 28 genera of 18 families in 14 countries.

29. *Cryptoparlatoresopsis halli* (Bodenheimer)

***Aonidia halli* Bodenheimer**

Common name: Hall scale.

Recorded by: Bodenheimer, 1929 on *Tamarix* sp. at Sinai Peninsula, Egypt.

Reported by: Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with *Punica granatum* (Lythraceae) and *Tamarix mannifera* (Tamaricaceae) in 6 countries.

30. *Cryptoparlatoresopsis meccae* (Hall)

***Targionia meccae* Hall**

Common name: Mecca scale.

Reported by: Danzig and Pellizzari 1998 in Egypt and Abd-Rabou and Evens, 2021.

Associated with *Diospyros kaki* (Ebenaceae), *Ziziphus* (Rhamnaceae) and *K. tamarix* (Tamaricaceae) in 6 countries.

31. *Diaspidiotus ancylus* (Putnam)

***Diaspis ancylus* Putnam**

***Aspidiotus howardi* Cockerell**

Common name: Howardi scale, putnam scale and maple bark scale.

حشرة الحور القشرية

Reported by: Abou-Elkhair, 2001 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021 on *Populus candicans*.

Associated with 56 genera of 38 families in 12 countries.

32. *Diaspidiotus ceconii* (Leonardi)

***Hemiberlesia ceconii* (Leonardi)**

Common name: Cecconi scale.

Recorded by: Hall, 1926 on *Ephedra foemineu*.

Reported by: Balachowsky, 1950 on *Deverra tortuosa* and *Asparagus aphyllus* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 12 genera of 10 families in 12 countries.

33. *Diaspidiotus ostreaformis* (Curtis)

***Aspidiotus ostreaformis* Curtis**

***Quadraspidotus ostreaformis* (Curtis)**

Common name: European fruit scale, false San Jose scale, green oyster scale and pear-tree oyster scale.

Reported by: Watosn, 2022.

Associated with 43 genera of 21 families in 61 countries.

34. *Diaspidiotus pyri* (Lichtenstein)

***Quadraspidiotus pyri* (Lichtenstein)**

***Quadraspidiotus aegyptiacus* (Hall)**

Common name: Yellow pear scale, pear oyster shell scale and fig scale.

حشرة الكمتري الصفراء

Recorded by: Hall, 1925 as *Aspidiotus ostreaeformis aegypticus* at Kafr El-Sheikh on fig trees.

Reported by: Bodenheimer, 1929 on *Olea europaea* at Wadi Ledscha, Sinai as *Aspidiotus sinaiticus*

; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *Quadraspidiotus pyri* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 15 genera of 9 families in 28 countries.

35. *Diaspis boisduvalii* Signoret

***Diaspidiotus boisduvalii* Signoret**

Common name: Boisduval scale and cocconut scale.

حشرة البذوفال القشرية

حشرة الأوركيد القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922, on unknown species of ornamental palm at Cairo.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada 1987; Moursi *et al.*, 1991a on *Echinocactus grusoni* in Egyptian western desert; Ghabbour, 1999 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

It is an economic and important pest of Orchids (Miller and Davidson, 2005).

Associated with 149 genera of 39 families in 90 countries.

36. *Diaspis bromeliae* (Kerner)

***Aspidiotus bromelia* Kerner**

Common name: Pinapple scale

حشرة الأناناس القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1925 on *Agave vivipara* and *Ocotea* sp.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Hydriastele* and *Agava*; Abd-Rabou, 2002; Watson, 2002 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 34 genera of 13 families in 78 countries.

37. *Diaspis echinocacti* (Bouché)

***Diaspis cacti* Comstock**

Common name: Cactus scale.

Recorded by: Newstead, 1911.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 as *Diaspis cacti* on *Opuntia* sp. all over Egypt; Ezzat, 1958; Abd-Rabou, 2001 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: Listed as a serious and widespread pest (Miller and Davidson, 1990).

Associated with 57 genera of 11 families in 78 countries.

38. *Duplachionaspis divergens* (Green)

***Duplachionaspis graminis* (Green)**

Chionaspis gramimis var divergens

Green

Common name: Bambo scale and bunch grass scale.

حشرة البامبو القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 for the first time as *Chionaspis graminis var divergens* on *Agrostis alba* at Helwan Road and Maadi, Cairo and in 1923 on *Arundo donax*, *Chryopogon zizanioides* and *Poa memoralis*.

Reported by: Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 19 genera of family Poaceae in 20 countries.

39. *Duplachionaspis monodi* (Rungs)

***Chionaspis noueae monodi* Rungs**

Common name: Unknown.

Reported by: Balachowsky, 1954 on *Stipagrostis pungens* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021

Note: It is close to *D. noaeae* but differ in having the gland Spines paired on Segement VII and VIII. It is known exclusively from grass (Balachowsky, 1954).

Associated with 3 genera of family Poaceae in 6 countries.

40. *Duplachionaspis natalensis*

(Maskell)

Chionaspis spartinae netalensis

Maskell

***Chionaspis stantophri* Cooley**

Common name: Buffalo grass scale and mango scale

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 as *Chionaspis graminis aegyptiaca* Hall on *Agrostis verticillata*, *A. donax* and *Imperata cylindrica*.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *Chionaspis stantophri*; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Phramites australis*; Abd-Rabou, 2001 on Cupressus and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 22 genera of 3 families in 19 countries.

41. *Duplachionaspis noaeae* (Hall)

***Chionaspis noaeae* Hall**

Common name: Goosefoot armored scale and thorny saltwort scale.

Recorded by: Hall, 1925 as *Chionaspis noaeae* on *Noaeae mucronata*, and on *Anabasis articulate*, *Erythrococca atrovirens* in 1927.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Moursi and Gomma, 1991, on *Anabasis articulata* shoots, *Haloxylon* sp., *Panicum targidum* at natural ecosystem, Egyptian western desert and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 11 genera of 3 families in 11 countries.

42. *Dynaspidiotus britanicus*

(Newstead)

***Aspidiotus britanicus* Newstead**

Common name: Oak scale, laural scale, holly scale and bay tree scale.

حشرة البلوط القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 as *Aspidiotus latastei* but misidentification discovered by Danzig, 1993.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Danzig and Pellizari, 1998; Mohammad and Ghabbour, 2008 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: Argyriou (1990) mentioned that it is considered a minor pest of olive in Mediterranean countries.

Associated with 36 genera of 22 families in 28 countries.

43. *Dynaspidiotus ephedrarum* (Lindinger)

***Aspidiotus ephedrarum* Lindinger**
***Ephedraspis epherrarum* Lindinger**
Common name: Sandy Cherry scale.

حشرة العمد القشرية

Recorded by: It is not recorded in Egypt according to scale net or Catalogue of life.

Reported by: Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *Ephedraspis ephedrarum* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021 on *Ephedra* sp in Eastern desert.

Associated with 3 genera (*Asparagus horridus*, *Ephedra* sp. and *Pinus* sp.) of 3 families (Asparagaceae, Ephedraceae and Pinaceae) in 18 countries.

44. *Fiorinia fioriniae* (Targioni Tozzetti)

***Diaspis fioriniae* Targioni Tozzetti**

Common name: Fiorina scale and avocado scale.

حشرة الفيورينا القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 at Alexandria only.

Reported by: Alfieri, 1929; Priesner and Hosny, 1940; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Phoenix dactylifera* and Mesbah *et al.*, 2001b on *Calistemon lonceolatus* and *Ruscus hypoglossum* at Sabahia Research Station, Alexandria, Egypt.

Associated with 119 genera of 54 families in 61 countries.

45. *Fiorinia phoenicis* Balachowsky

Common name: Fiorinia date scale and oriental yellow scale.

الحشره القشريه الشرقيه الصفراء

Recorded by: Balachowsky, 1967, who mentioned that it is a new pest on date palm in Egypt.

Reported by: Ghabbour and Mohammad (2010) who mentioned that it was collected and identified in the Department of Scale insects and mealy bugs, Plant Protection Institutes; Elwan *et al.*, 2011 and Radwan, 2012.

Associated with one genus (*Phoenix dactylifera*) of family Arecaceae in 4 countries.

46. *Furchadaspis zamiae* (Morgan)

***Diaspis zamiae*. Morgan**

Common name: Zamia scale and cycad scale.

حشرة السيكادا القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1926.

Reported by: Alfieri, 1929; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996; Abd-Rabou, 2000 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 19 genera of 10 families in 44 countries.

47. *Gonaspidotus seurati* (Marchal) *Aspidiotus (Hemiberlesia) seurati* Marchall

***Abgrallaspis seurati* (Marchal)**

Common name: Seurat scale.

Reported by: Balachowsky, 1927 and 1932; Ezzat, 1958 as *Abgrallaspis seurati* (Marchal);

Ezzat and Nada, 1987 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 6 genera of 5 families in 5 countries.

48. *Hemiberlesia cyanophylli* (Signoret)

***Aspidiotus cyanophylli* Signoret**

***Abgrallaspis cyanophylli* (Signoret)**

Common name: Cynophyllum scale.

حشرة العنتاب القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 and 1923 on guava trees at Geziret Debsha Markaz El-Aiyat, Lower Egypt) in 1920 and on *Ceratonia seliqua*, *Ficus sycomorus*, *Phyllanthus*, *Jasminium*, and *Dorgalis coffae*. He said that it is not very common but has been collected in widely separate locations.

Reported by: Priesner and Hosny, 1940; Ezzat, 1958 as *Abgrallaspis cyanophylli*; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *A. cyanophylli*; Mesbah *et al.*, 2001a on *Acacia saligna*. at Burg el-Arab; **Abou-Elkhair**, 2001; Abd-Rabou, 2004 on *Arcentum pitechrdia* in Kom-Ombo and Sliwa and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 176 genera of 77 families in 80 countries.

49. *Hemiberlesia lataniae* (Signoret) *Aspidiotus lataniae* Signoret

***Aspidiotus cydoniae* Comstock**

Common name: Grape vine scale and latania scale.

حشرة اللاتانيا القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 and 1923 as *Aspidiotus cydoniae* for the first time in Egypt, who mentioned that it is more common in lower than the Upper Egypt, attacks many hosts of the ornamental plants such as Ficus, Rose and *Jusminium humali*.

Reported by: Bodenheimer, 1924 as *Aspidiotus lataniae* in El Arish; Ezzat, 1958; Moursi and Hegazi, 1983 on *Thymelaea hirsute* leaves and brancher at Burg el- Arab and Omayed sites, North Coast of Egypt; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Mesbah *et al.*, 2001a on *Acacia saligna* at Fuka and Matrouh and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 370 genera of 120 families in 153 countries.

50. *Hemibertesia rapax* (Comstock)

***Aspidiotus rapax* Comstock**

***Aspidiotus camelliae* (Comstock)**

Common name: Camellia scale, apple scale and greedy scale.

حشرة التفاح القشرية

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Mesbah *et al.*, 2002b on pear trees all over the year under dry farm system at Burg el. Arab; Moursi *et al.*, 2010. on apple, apricot, in Burg el Arab and Hammam site, Western desert and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: It is an important quarantine insect pest in Egypt, according to Gill, 1997, Claps *et al.*, 2001 and Foldi, 2001.

Associated with 210 genera of 86 families in 94 countries.

51. *Howardia biclavis* (Comstock)

***Chionaspis biclavis* Comstock**

Common name: Mining scale and burrowing scale.

Reported by: Watson and Kondo, 2022 for the first time in Egypt.

Note: It is highly polyphagous species that infests the bark, woody hosts,

according to Davidson and Miller, 1999.

Associated with 221 genera of 76 families in 84 countries.

52 *Ischnaspis longirostris* (Signoret)

***Mytalaspis longirostris* Signoret**

***Ischnaspis filiformis* Doug**

Common name: Black thead scale and black line scale.

الحشرة القشرية خطية الشكل

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 as *Ischnaspis longirostris* = *I. filiformis*, collected in Alexandria.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Agave americana*; Abd-Rabou, 2000 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 162 genera of 55 families in 102 countries.

53. *Lepidosaphes beckii* (Newman)

Common name: Purple scale and citrus mussle scale.

الحشرة القشرية الارجوانية

Recorded by: Newsteads, 1907.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 as *Lepidosaphes (Mytiluspis) beckii* on citrus at North of Delta, Qalyubiya, Minofya, Alexandria, Rosetta, Damietta and Port Said; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Abd-Rabou, 2001; Badr, 2014 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 73 genera of 49 families in 162 countries.

54. *Lepidosaphes conchiformis*

(Gmelin)

***Coccus conchiformis* Gmelin**

***Lepidosaphes minima* Newstead**

***Lepidosaphes ficus* (Signoret)**

Common name: Fig oystershell scale and Mediterranean fig scale.

حشرة التين القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 and 1923 as *Lepidosaphes (Mytiluspis) ficus*, on fig trees in Cairo.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *Lepidosaphes ficus*; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 as *L. ficus* on *Punica granatum* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 41 genera of 24 families in 47 countries.

55. *Lepidosaphes gloverii* (Packard)

***Aspidiotus gloverii* Packard**

***Insulaspis gloverii* (Packard)**

Common name: Citrus long scale, glover scale and long mussel scale.

حشرة الموالح المحارية المطاولة

Recorded by: Hall, 1924 on *Annona*, *Ficus*, *Washingtonia filifera*, *Asparagus setacens*, *Psidium guajava*, *Citrus*, *Populus*, *Salix*, *Vitis*, *Musa paradisiacal*.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958 as *L. gloveri*; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Mangifera indica*; Abd-Rabou, 2001 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 48 genera of 30 families in 105 countries.

56. *Lepidosaphes pallidula* (Fernald)

***Lepidosaphes pallida* Fernald**

***Mytiluspis pallide* Green**

Common name: Mango scale.

حشرة المانجو القشرية

Reported by: Hosny and Ezzat, 1965; Habib *et al.*, 1971; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996; Elwan, 2005 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 11 genera of 10 families in 7 countries.

57. *Lepidosaphes pinnaeformis*

(Bouché)

***Aspidiotus pinnaeformis* Bouché**

***Mytiluspis pinnaeformis* Bouché**

Common name: Cymbidium scale and mussel scale.

Reported by: Archangelskaya, 1937 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: It is a pest of orchids in greenhouses as mentioned by Danzig, 1993.

Associated with 36 genera of 21 families in 37 countries.

58. *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* Williams

***Insulaspis tapleyi* Borchsenius**

Common name: Guava long scale and oyster scale.

حشرة الجوافة القشرية المطاولة

Recorded by: Swailem, 1972 for the first time in Egypt on guava, mango, ficus, *E. sycamorns*, *Jasminum humils*, *J. sambae*, *Nerium oleander*, *Olea europaea*, *Rose* sp., *Eucalyptus* sp., *Aberio coffra*, *Ceratonia siliqua* and *Sterculia diversifolia*.

Reported by: Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Moursi *et al.*, 1991a in Alexandria and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 28 genera of 19 families in 16 countries.

59. *Lepidosaphes ulmi* (Linnaeus)
***Coccus ulmi* Linnaeus**

***Lepidosaphes pomorum* Bouché**

Common name: Apple oyster shell and oyster shell scale

حشرة التفاح القشرية

Recorded by: Newstead, 1906 and 1907 on *Populus*, *Pelargonium* as *Lepidosaphes (Mytilaspis) bicolor* at Giza.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 as *Lepidosaphes (Mytilaspis) ulmi* = *L. pomorum* on Vines, Ziziphus, Seshania, Pigeon, pear, poplar and willow; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 169 genera of 74 families in 72 countries.

60. *Leucaspis Pini* (Hartig)

***Aspidiotus pini* Hartig**

***Leucaspis affini* Leonardi**

Common name: Pine scale, hartig's pine scale and white pine scale.

حشرة الصنوبر القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 as *Leucaspis affini* on *Pinus* sp. all over Egypt.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Badr, 2014 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with all pinus species in 29 countries (3 families and 5 genera).

61. *Leucaspis pusilla* Löw

Common name: Pusilla scale and small pine scale

حشرة الصنوبر القشرية الصغيرة

حشرة البسيلا القشريه

Recorded by: Newstead, 1907.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 and 1923 on *Pinus helepensis* all over Egypt; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Mohammad and Ghabbour, 2008 ; Badr, 2014 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 4 genera of 2 families in 36 countries.

62. *Leucaspis riccae* Targioni Tazzetti

Common name: White olive scale.

حشرة الزيتون المحارية البيضاء

Recorded by: Newstead, 1913.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 who mentioned that it fairly common and widely distributed throughout Egypt; Ezzat, 1958; Moursi and Hegazi, 1983; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 6 genera of 6 families in 19 countries (North Africa and Mediterranean basin countries)

63. *Lindingaspis floridana* Ferries

Common name: Floridana scale.

حشرة الفلوريدانا القشرية

Recorded by: Hosny and Ezzat, 1957 on *Mangifera indica* for the first time in Egypt.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Abd-Rabou, 2001 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 5 genera of 5 families in 9 countries.

64. *Lindingaspis greeni* (Brain and Kelly)

***Chrysomphalus greeni* Brain and Kelly**

Common name: Unknown.

Reported by: In Egypt only by Porcelli and Pellizzari (2019) and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 4 genera of 4 families in 4 countries.

Capparis moonii (Capparaceae), *Punica granatum* (Lythraceae), *Ficus cyathistipula*, *F. microcarpa* (Moraceae) and *Choetachma aristata* (Ulmaceae).

65. *Lindingaspis rossi* (Maskell)

***Aspidiotus rossi* Maskell**

Common name: Araucaria black scale, ross scale and round black scale.

حشرة الاروكاريا القشرية

Recorded by: Swaillem *et al.*, 1976 for the first time on ornamental plants.

Reported by: Moursi *et al.*, 1991a; Badr, 2014 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 110 genera of 60 families in 43 countries.

66. *Lineaspis striata* (Newstead)

***Chionaspis striata* Newstead**

Common name: Cypress snow scale.

حشرة الجليد القشرية

Recorded by: Lindinger, 1910 on *Tetraclinis articulata*.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 as *Chionaspis striata* on Thuja trees in lower Egypt, particularly in Alexandria and Coastal area, and also on *Capressus* sp.; Ezzat, 1958 as *Chionaspis striata*; Borchsenius, 1961 as *L. thelophlora* at Cairo on *Thuja* sp.; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Moursi *et al.*, 2001 as *Chionaspis striata* on *Thuja orientalis* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 10 genera of 5 families in 17 countries.

67. *Melanaspis glomerata* Green

Aspidiotus (Targionia) glomeratus

Green

Common name: Sugar cane scale and black scale.

Recorded by: Hall, 1926.

Reported by: Balachowsky, 1927; Prisnier and Hosny, 1940; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 and Abd-Rabou and Moustafa, 2006.

Associated with one genus (*Saccharum officinarum*) of family Poaceae in 3 countries.

68. *Melanaspis inopinata* (Leonardi)

***Aonidiella inopinata* Leonardi**

Common name: Deciduous scale and deciduous fruit scale.

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 on *Malus prunifolia*, *Prunus armeniaca* and *Pyrus communis*.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Abd-Rabou, 2000 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 28 genera of 14 families in 14 countries.

69. *Mercetaspis bicuspis* (Hall)

***Lepidosaphes bicuspis* Hall**

***Nilotaspis bicuspis* Hall**

***Acanthomytilus bicuspis* (Hall)**

Common name: Cupsid scale

الحشرة القشرية ذات الطرف المدبب

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 on Tamarix in Armant, Upper Egypt as *Lepidosaphes bicuspis*.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966 as *Acanthomytilus bicuspis* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 3 genera of 3 families in 4 countries.

70. *Mercetaspis halli* (Green)

***Nilotaspis halli* (Green)**

***Lepidosaphes halli* Green**

Common name: Hall scale and peach scale.

حشرة الخوخ القشرية

Recorded by: Green, 1923 as *Lepidosaphes halli*.

Reported by: Hall, 1923; Priesner and Hosny, 1940; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *Nilotaspis halli*; Moursi *et al.*, 1991a as *Nilotaspis halli* on Almond at rain-Fed farms, Burg el-Arab area, Alexandria, Egypt; Miller and Davidson, 2005 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 14 genera of 5 families in 20 countries.

71. *Mercetaspis isis* (Hall)

***Nilotaspis isis* (Hall)**

***Coccomytilus isis* Hall**

Common name: Isis scale.

حشرة ايزيس القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 and 1926 as *Coccomytilus isis* on *Tamarix* sp. in Luxor, Egypt.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada 1987 as *Nilotaspis isis* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with *Tamarix* spp. of Family Tamaricaceae in 9 countries.

72. *Mongrovaspis quadrispinosa* (Green)

Leucaspis quadrispinosa Green

Common name: Mangrove scale.

Recorded by: Green, 1934 on *Avicennia officinalis* in Mersa Halaib.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with *Avicennia* spp. of family Acanthaceae in 4 countries.

73. *Morganella longispina* (Morgan)

Aspidiotus longispina Morgan

Common name: Chanpuca scale, maskell scale and long spine scale.

الحشرة القشرية ذات الذيل الطويل

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 87 genera of 44 families in 49 countries.

74. *Mycetaspis personata* (Comstock)

Aspidiotus personatus Comstock

Chrysomphalus personatus

(Comstock)

Common name: Masked scale and personata scale.

حشرة البرسوناتا القشرية

Recorded by: Priesner and Hosny, 1932 on *Ficus* sp., *Lantana aurea* and *Anacridium accidental* in Alexandria during January.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; El-Minshawy and Osman, 1973 and 1974 on *Hydra halix* Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Mourad *et al.*, 2001 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 33 genera of 21 families in 54 countries.

75. *Oceanaspidotus spinosus* (Comstock)

Aspidiotus spinosus Comstock

Common name: Avocado scale, spined scale and spinose scale.

Reported by: Abou-Elkhair, 2001 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 79 genera of 48 families in 48 countries.

76. *Odonaspis panici* (Hall)

***Aonidia panici* (Hall)**

Common name: Panic scale

حشرة الدخن القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1926 on *Panicum turgidum* in Abu Sueir.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Balachowsky, 1953; Borchsenius, 1966; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ben-Dov, 1988 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with *Cenchrus* sp. and *Panicum* sp. of family Poaceae in 6 countries.

77. *Odonaspis ruthae* Kotinsky

Odonasps graminis Kotinsky

Common name: Hard grass scale and Bermuda grass scale.

حشرة نجيل برمودا القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1925 on *Cynodon dactylon*.

Reported by: Green, 1937; Ferris, 1938; Hosny, 1939; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ben-Dov, 1988 on *Andropagan cuttleeye* and *Axonopus compressus* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 32 genera of 6 families in 47 countries.

78. *Osiraspis balteata* Hall

Common name: Belted scale

الحشرة القشرية ذات الحزام

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 on *Tamarix* sp. in Luxor, Egypt.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: According to Hall, 1923, the female scale is not easy to find, being small and hidden in the smallest crevice or at the base of a broad shallow pit covered by male scale.

Associated with one genus (*Tamarix*) from one family in one country (Egypt).

79. *Pallulaspis retamae* (Hall)

Nilotaspis retamae (Hall)

Cocco-mytilus retamae Hall

Common name: Retama scale

حشرة الرتم القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1926 on *Retama retam* and *Artemisia* sp. at Wadi Ibtadi, Camel ride, Helwan, Egypt as *Cocceomytilus retamae*.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958 as *Nilotaspis retamae*; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Artemisia* and *Retama* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 2 genera of 2 families in 3 countries.

80 *Parlatoareopsis chinensis* (Marlatt) *Parlatoria chinensis* Marlatt

Common name: Chinese obscure scale
Recorded by: Hall, 1922 as *Parlatoria chinensis* = *Chionaspis longispina* on *Justicia alba*, *Albizia lebbak* and *Bauhinia* sp. at Luxor and Beni Suef in Upper Egypt.

Reported by: Chen and Wong, 1936 on *Ziziphus jujuba* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: Marlatt collected it in 1902 at Cairo on an unknown plant. He said that it is in conjunction with *P. affinis* = *P. calfanthing* and the Egyptian variety differ slightly in the exterior secretion of the median lobes, these serration or notches being reduced to two or three instead of four or more and Central lobular projection is somewhat larger.

Associated with 55 genera of 25 families in 8 countries.

81. *Parlatoareopsis longispina* (Newstead)

***Chionaspis longispina* Newstead**

***Parlatoareopsis perplexus* McKenzie**

Common name: Asiatic pomegranate scale and long spines scale.

الحشرة القشرية ذات الشوك الطويل
حشرة الرمان القشرية

Recorded by: Newstead, 1911 on *Justicia alba*, *Agave americana*, *Bauhinia acuminata*, *Jasminum* sp., *Nerium oleander*, *Opuntia humilis* and *Punica granatum*, at Ghezireh, Cairo, Egypt.

Reported by: Hall, 1922; McKenzie, 1952 as *Parlatoria perplexus* on

Nerium oleander at the ground of Heliopolis palace Hotel; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad 1996 on *Agave americana*, and *Opuntia* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021 on *Jasminum*.

Associated with 35 genera of 22 families in 10 countries.

82. *Parlatoria blanchardii* (Targion: Tozzetti)

***Aonidia blanchardii* Targian, Tozzetti**

Common name: Date palm scale and parlatoria date scale.

حشرة النخيل القشرية

Recorded by: Newstead, 1906.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 on *Phoenix dactylifera* and *Latania* sp. all over the Country. He added that this species is very common on date palms throughout Egypt; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Moursi *et al.*, 1991a on *Jasminem* sp. and *Lantana camara*; Mourad and Zanuncio, 1998 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 13 genera of 5 families in 42 countries.

83. *Parlatoria camelliae* Comstock

***Parlatoria pergandii camelliae* Comstock**

Common name: Camellia parlatoria scale.

Recorded by: Danzing and Pellizzari, 1998 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: According to McKenzie, 1945, it is close to *Parlatoria crotonis* but the absence of strongly sclerotized ocular Spur immediately separates it from the latter.

Associated with 43 genera of 27 families in 30 countries.

84. *Parlatoria crotonis* Douglas

***Parlateria proteus crotonis* Douglas**

Common name: Croton parlatoria scale

حشرة الكروتون القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1925.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Citrus sinensis*

and *C. medica* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021 on *Citrus aurantium*.

Associated with 15 genera of 14 families in 51 countries.

85. *Parlatoria crypta* Mc Kenzie

Common name: Mango white scale.

Recorded by: Jansen and Alferink, 2023 for the first time in Egypt on *Mangifera indica*.

Associated with 42 genera of 27 families in 12 countries.

86. *Parlatoria ephedrae* (Lindinger)

***Parlatoria ephedrae* Lind.**

***Genaparlatoria ephedrae* (Lindinger)**

Common name: Ephedra scale.

Recorded by: Hall, 1925.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 1 genus (*Ephedra*) of family Ephedraceae in 5 countries.

87. *Parlatoria oleae* (Colvée)

***Diaspis oleae* Colvée**

Common name: Olive scale and plum scale.

حشرة الزيتون القشرية

حشرة الخوخ القشرية

Recorded by: Newstead, 1906.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 on *Shinus trebinthifolius*, *Nerium oleander*, *Ficus*, *Prunus americana* and, *P. persicae*; Ezzat, 1958 on *Ligustrum ovalifolium*; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabour and Mohammad, 1996 on citrus and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 133 genera of 56 families in 63 countries.

88. *Parlatoria pergandii* Comstock

***Parlatoria sinensis* Mask**

Common name: Chaff scale and black parlatoria scale.

حشرة الموالح القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 on citrus.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Moursi *et al.*, 2013 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 66 genera of 37 families in 106 countries.

89. *Parlatoria proteus* (Curtis)

***Aspidiotus proteus* Curtis**

Common name: Small brown scale, proteus scale and orchid parlatoria scale.

حشرة الفضة القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 on unknown ornamental palm at Cairo.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Talhouk, 1975 as a minor pest of Citrus in Egypt; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Ruscus aculeatus*, *Ruscus hypophyllum* and *Camellia sasanqua* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 161 genera of 55 families in 75 countries.

90. *Parlateria ziziphi* (Lucas)

Common name: Nabk scale and black parlataria scale.

حشرة النبق القشرية

Recorded by: Newstead, 1911.

Reported by: Hosny 1943 on mandarin at Alexandria, who reported that it is an important pest of citrus in Egypt; Ezzat, 1958; Talhouk, 1973; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 19 genera of 14 families in 102 countries.

91. *Pinnaspis aspidistrae* (Signoret)

***Chionaspis aspidistra* Signoret**

Common name: Aspidistra scale, fern scale and Brazilian snow scale.

الحشرة القشرية الثلجية

Recorded by: Hall, 1923 on *Rohden japonica*.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Tamarix* sp and *Pandanus* sp. and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 159 genera of 78 families in 115 countries.

92. *Pinnaspis buxi* (Bouché)

***Aspidiotus buxi* Bouché**

Common name: Bamboo mussel scale and beechwood scale.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 102 genera of 49 families in 79 countries.

93. *Pinnaspis strachani* (Cooley)

***Chionaspis minor* Cooley**

Common name: Cotton white scale and hibiscus snow scale.

Recorded by: Not recorded in Egypt before.

Reported by: Abou-Elkhair, 2001 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 265 genera of 79 families in 130 countries.

94. *Prodiaspis sinensis* (Tang)

***Prodiaspis tamaricicola* Young**

***Adiscodaspis sinensis* Tang**

Common name: Unknown.

Reported by: Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: Tang, 1986 showed that *Adiscodaspis sinensis* is close to *A. tamaricicola* but differs in antenna of *A. sinensis* of the form with 4 thin setae and the all 3rd segments of the antenna in the first stage are the longest. The marginal groups of dorsal ducts 14 in number on each side of the abdomen.

Associated with 2 genera (*Tamarix* and *Myricaris*) of one family Tamaricaceae in 2 countries (China and Egypt).

95. *Pseudaonidia trilobitiformis* (Green)

***Aspidiotus trilobitiformis* Green**

Common name: Cashew scale, gingging scale and trilobe scale.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 130 genera of 57 families in 100 countries.

96. *Pseudaulacaspis cockerelli* (Cooley)

***Chionaspis cockerelli* Cooley**

Common name: False oleander scale, fullaway oleander scale and magnolia white scale.

Recorded by: Green, 1937.

Reported by: Gilliomee, 1966 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Note: Listed as a pest of ornamental plants by Miller and Davidson 1990.

Associated with 174 genera of 90 families in 59 countries.

97. *Pseudaulacaspis pentagona*

(Targioni Tozzetti)

***Diaspis pentagona* Targioni Tozzetti**

***Aulacaspis pentagona* Hall**

Common name: White peach scale and white plum scale.

حشرة الخوخ القشرية البيضاء

Recorded by: Hall, 1922 as

Aulacaspis (Dinspis) pentagona on *Rose* sp. and *Prunus armenica* in Alexandria for the first time.

Reported by: Alfieri, 1929; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987; Moursi *et al.*, 1991a on *Ipomae* sp., *Catalpa* sp. and *Rose* sp.; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Draceana*, *Acacia nilotica* and *Spiraea japonica*; **Abou-Elkhair**, 2001 on *Geodorum densiflorum* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 261 genera of 91 families in 131 countries.

98. *Pseudatargionia glandulosa* (Newstead)

***Aonidia glandulosa* Newstead**

Common name: Newstead acacia scale.

حشرة السنط القشرية

Recorded by: Newstead, 1911 for the first time on "Sunt" *Acacia arabica* in Upper Egypt.

Reported by: Hall, 1922 and 1923 on *Acacia nilotica* and *Acacia tortillis* as *Aonidia glandulosa* and mentioned that it is common in Cairo and Upper Egypt but has not been collected in lower Egypt; Priesner and Hosny, 1940; Ezzat, 1958; Ben-Dov, 1974; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 2 genera of 2 families in 15 countries.

99. *Rhizaspidotus adiscus* Gómez-Minor Ortega

Rhizospidotus artemisia adiscus

Gómez-Miner Ortega

Common name: Unknown.

Reported by: Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021 only in Egypt from Western desert.

Note: It was distinguished by Gómez Minor Ortega, 1968 from *Rhizaspidotus artemisia artemisia* only by the absence of previvular disc pores.

Associated with genus *Artemisia* of family (Asteraceae) in Egypt and Spain countries.

100. *Rhizaspidotus canariensis*

(Lindinger)

Aspidiotus canariensis Lindinger

Rhizaspidiolus artemisiae (Hall)

Common name: Artemisia scale.

حشرة الشيح القشرية

Recorded by: Hall, 1926 on *Artemisia monosperma* as *Aspidiotus artemisiae* at Seuz Road.

Reported by: Bodenheimer, 1935 in Sinai; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *Rhizaspidotus artemisiae*; Moursi et al., 1991a on *Achilla fragrantissima*; Moursi and Gomma 1991 on *Artemisia judaica* and *A. monosperma* at Egyptian North Coast and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 17 genera of 7 families in 20 countries.

101. *Rungaspis capparidis*

(Bodenheimer)

Diaspis capparids Bodenheimer

Common name: Caparris scale.

Recorded by: Bodenheimer, 1929 on *Capparis galeata* and *Capparis siniaca* in Sinai Peninsula, Wadi Isle.

Reported by: Ben-Dov, 1980 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021 on *Capparis cartilaginea* (= *C. galeata*).

Associated with 12 genera of 10 families in 7 countries.

102. *Salicicola kermanensis*

(Lindinger)

Crythemichionaspis africana Newstead

Frorinia africana Newstead

Common name: Willow scale and Iranian popular scale.

حشرة الصفصاف القشرية

Recorded by: Newstead, 1911 as *Fiorinia africana* on *Populus* sp. at gardens of the Horticultural Society, Giza, Egypt.

Reported by: Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Nada, 1987 as *Salicicola Africana*; Ghabbour and Mohammad, 1996 on *Salix mucronate* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 7 genera of 6 families in 19 countries.

103. *Suturaspis pistaciae* (Lindinger)

Leucaspis pistaciae Lindinger

Common name: Pistacia scale

حشرة الفستق القشرية

Recorded by: Bodenheimer, 1937.

Reported by: Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 1 genus (*Pistacia*) of family Anacardiaceae in 10 countries.

104. *Targionia haloxyloni* Hall

Common name: Haloxylon scale.

Recorded by: Hall, 1926 on *Haloxylon schweinfurthii* in Eastern desert, Wadi Askhar, south Wadi Araba, Wadi Sennur.

Reported by: Ferris, 1943; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Afifi, 1966; Ezzat and Nada 1987; Moursi and Gomma 1991 on *Haloxylon* sp., *Halexylon salicornicum*, *H. Schweinfurthii*, *H. tamariscifolium* and *Helianthemum lippi* and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 7 genera of 5 families in 5 countries.

105. *Targionia nigra* Signoret

Common name: Unknown.

Recorded by: Hall, 1923, 1925 and 1926 on *Alhagi maurorum* (1923) and on *Forsetia aegyptia* (1925) and on *Ochradenus baccatus* (1926).

Reported by: Bodenheimer, 1924; Balachowsky, 1951; Ferris 1943; Ezzat, 1958 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 31 genera of 15 families in 17 countries.

106. *Unaspis citri* (Comstock)

Chionaspis citri Comstock.

***Chionaspis eunymi* Comstock
(Missidentified)**

Common name: Citrus snow scale and white snow scale.

Recorded by: Newstead, 1907 on *Euonymus Japonica*.

Reported by: Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 24 genera of 17 families in 102 countries.

107. *Unaspis eunymi* (Comstock)

***Chionaspis euonymi* Comstock**

Common name: Spindle berry scale and euonymus scale.

Recorded by: Balachowsky, 1954.

Reported by: Danzig and Pellazzirie, 1998 and Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2021.

Associated with 35 genera of 22 families in 41 countries.

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